

Local Government in India

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in India	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in India: An Introduction	7
2.2. <i>School, Educational Services and their Delivery Mechanisms</i>	10
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in India: An Introduction.....	15
3.2. <i>Fiscal Autonomy: Restraints and Limits</i>	18
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in India: An Introduction	23
4.2. <i>Decentralization and Democratic Governance</i>	27
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in India: An Introduction.....	31
5.2. <i>Local Governments and their Functioning</i>	33
6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in India: An Introduction	40
6.2. <i>Sanitation Development</i>	43

Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in India: An Introduction

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India follows a devolved system of decentralization in which the states are responsible for the devolution of powers to the urban and rural local authorities. At the local level, intergovernmental relationships exist between different tiers of local rural government. The administrative units at each state level have their own historical trajectory and a uniform pattern does not exist for each state. Each state has its own administrative units and structures. Therefore, a certain amount of friction is bound to arise over operational guidelines and implementation for different projects and delivery of services. The state government looks over various projects and plans and decides on the devolution of powers and functions for these activities and projects. A three-tier system works at the local levels which are accountable to state government.¹³ Similarly, the decentralization of power and decision-making works at all levels from the center to the states.

There are several federal bodies and inter-governmental organizations such as inter-state councils, district boards and committees of various kinds which have been formed from time to time to work towards establishing the intergovernmental relations between the lower and higher levels of administration. In doing so, regional development boards and units are also set up by different states from time to time. With the rapid urbanization that the Indian cities are experiencing, it is imperative that cities act as the main catalyst of development. This level of coordination between center, state and local government is crucial for the development and growth of large cities.

Thus, for the cities to generate 'agglomeration economies', the imbalance between responsibilities and finances must be worked out.¹⁴ The relationship between *panchayats*, urban local units and government departments has been a domain of contestation and messy politics.

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¹³ For more detail, see report section 4.2. on Decentralization and Democratic Governance.

¹⁴ Isher J Ahluwalia and others, 'State of Municipal Finances in India' (Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations 2019).

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